

Low Order Natural Guide Star Selection Tool and Sky Coverage Update for TMT NFIRAOS

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ABSTRACT

LGS-based MCAO systems require multiple (typically up to three) low-order NGS WFSs to measure modes that are not observable by the LGS WFS, such as tip/tilt, focus, and plate scale (including astigmatism). Diffraction-limited WFSs operating in the infrared are often used to improve measurement precision while relaxing the guide star brightness requirements. However, finding NGSs that are both sufficiently bright and located close enough to the science field is often challenging—especially near the Galactic Pole, where star density is lowest.

When a mix of brighter and dimmer NGSs must be used, they often require different exposure times to balance correction quality and noise propagation. For instance, vibration and telescope wind shake demand higher bandwidth, whereas focus and plate scale modes require significantly lower bandwidth. In this paper, we present a multi-rate controller that effectively decouples the fast and slow low-order control loops to achieve optimal correction.

Complicating the problem further, correction of plate scale modes benefits from NGSs that are widely separated in order to provide sufficient lever arms. However, guide stars located farther from the science field typically receive less AO correction and therefore suffer from lower signal-to-noise ratios. Additionally, non-linearity and aliasing effects in the WFS render analytic performance models unreliable.

All of these factors contribute to the complexity of guide star selection in support of scientific observations. In this paper, we explore methods for predicting the performance of different guide star combinations with accuracy comparable to that of end-to-end physical optics simulations, enabling the selection of the optimal asterism. This tool also facilitates straightforward reevaluation of sky coverage under varying conditions, such as different guide star catalog limiting magnitudes or patrol field constraints.

Keywords: Adaptive Optics, Low Order Control, Machine Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive optics (AO) has become an indispensable technology for ground-based astronomical telescopes, enabling diffraction-limited observations by compensating in real time for phase perturbations introduced by atmospheric turbulence, as well as dome seeing, vibration, and telescope wind shake. Multi-conjugate adaptive optics (MCAO) extends the corrected field of view using tomographic reconstruction of atmospheric layers with multiple guide stars and applying correction using multiple deformable mirrors [1, 2].

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Laser guide stars (LGSs) further enhance the usefulness of AO systems by dramatically increasing sky coverage compared with systems relying solely on natural guide stars (NGSs). However, LGSs are fundamentally unable to measure certain low-order modes such as tip/tilt and focus due to the finite altitude of the artificial beacons and the absence of an absolute position reference [3]. MCAO designs therefore incorporate multiple low-order NGS wavefront sensors (WFSs) to recover these essential modes [4, 5].

The requirement for multiple NGSs to measure low-order modes places significant constraints on sky coverage, particularly near high Galactic latitudes where star density is lowest. Infrared diffraction-limited low-order NGS WFSs are therefore often used to relax guide star brightness requirements and improve measurement precision. Sky coverage studies have shown that the availability of three suitable NGSs within a given patrol field can still be very limited, particularly near the Galactic poles [6, 7].

In practice, guide stars of different brightness require different temporal sampling frequencies to optimize the trade-off between measurement noise and rejection bandwidth. High bandwidth is critical to mitigate fast disturbances such as telescope wind shake and vibrations, whereas slow modes such as focus and plate scale vary more gradually and can be measured at lower rates, reducing noise propagation and relaxing guide star brightness requirements. This motivates a multi-rate control architecture that effectively decouples fast and slow low-order control loops to achieve optimal overall correction [8, 9].

The geometric distribution of NGSs also plays a critical role in the reconstruction of plate scale because widely separated stars provide larger lever arms for these measurements [10, 11]. However, stars that are more widely separated from the science field often receive diminished AO sharpening, resulting in reduced signal-to-noise ratio and increased aliasing errors in the measurements [12, 13]. Consequently, predicting the performance of different guide star asterisms typically requires high-fidelity end-to-end physical optics simulations, which are computationally expensive to evaluate over large regions of parameter space.

In this paper, we present a machine learning-based method for predicting the performance of different NGS combinations with fidelity comparable to end-to-end simulations, but with significantly faster computation and near-instant results. This approach enables the selection of the optimal asterism for a given science target, as well as straightforward reevaluation of sky coverage under varying conditions, such as different guide star statistics or patrol field constraints.

Section 2 describes the NFIRAOS configuration and the turbulence conditions used in the simulations. Section 3 presents the multi-rate low-order control strategy. Section 4 introduces the machine learning-based approach for predicting low-order control performance. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the conclusions.

2. NFIRAOS

The TMT NFIRAOS [14] is an MCAO system with two deformable mirrors (DMs) conjugated to ranges of zero and 11.8 km. An asterism of five sodium LGS arranged in a pentagon of 35" radius plus 6th on axis are sensed by LGS WFS. Up to three NGS are picked off by low-order on-instrument wavefront sensors.

The performance requirements for NFIRAOS include diffraction-limited turbulence compensation from 0.8 μ m to 2.5 μ m over fields of view of up to 34"x34". The NGSs are acquired via probe arms within a 2' diameter patrol field of view. The NGS WFSs will operate in the near infrared (NIR; J, H and Ks bands) to take advantage of sharpening of the stars by NFIRAOS. In addition, NIR NGSs are more likely to be available especially in regions which are obscured by dust. Faint halo stars are also more likely to be red, which increases the number of potential NGSs at a given magnitude. The WFS pixel size (12 or 6mas) is matched to the Nyquist sampling of the PSF (in H band) to improve the linearity and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). Additional system and simulation parameters are summarized in Table 2.

The split tomography control algorithm will be used in both sky coverage simulations and the actual real time controller for NFIRAOS. In this control algorithm, the separate LGS and NGS control loops are driven independently. The atmospheric tomography step of the LGS control loop applies a minimum variance estimator [15] to tip/tilt and focus removed, pseudo open loop LGS WFS gradients. The NGS control loop uses a noise-weighted, least-squares reconstructor, and can operate at a different frame rate than the LGS loop depending upon the brightness of the NGS. The separation between the LGS and NGS loops is improved by nulling the

Table 1. C_n^2 profile models for the Mauna Kea 13N site.

Altitude (km)	25 Percentile $r_0 = 0.247\text{m}$	Median $r_0 = 0.186\text{m}$	75 Percentile $r_0 = 0.135\text{m}$	wind speed (m/s)
0	0.5152	0.4557	0.3952	5.6
0.5	0.0951	0.1295	0.1665	5.8
1	0.0322	0.0442	0.0703	6.3
2	0.0262	0.0506	0.0773	7.6
4	0.116	0.1167	0.0995	13.3
8	0.0737	0.0926	0.1069	19.1
16	0.1416	0.1107	0.0843	12.1

Table 2. NFIRAOS and atmospheric simulation parameters.

Parameter	Value
Telescope diameter (D)	30 m
Turbulence outer scale [18]	30 m
Telescope wind shake (75 Percentile)	28 mas
Mechanical vibration (uniform distribution between 5-20 Hz)	15 mas
Mean height of sodium LGS (h_s)	90 km
DM conjugate altitudes (h_c)	0, 11.8 km
AO order of correction	60×60
Detector passband	J, H, and Ks: [1.25 1.65 2.15]μm
Detector pixel size	12 (2x2) or 6 mas
Detector quantum efficiency	0.7
Detector read out noise	0.8e ⁻ /pixel/read
Detector excessive noise factor	1.2
End-to-end optical throughput for NGS WFS	[0.55 0.58 0.32]
Sky background	[16.2 13.9 14.9] magnitude/arcsec ²
Flux of zero magnitude star (each band)[19]	[3.22 2.82 1.51]×10 ⁹ photons/m ² /s
NGS limiting magnitude	22
Number of TTF WFS (2×2 subapertures)	1
Number of TT WFS (single subaperture)	2
Science FoV	34"×34" square
NGS patrol field FoV	2' diameter circular FoV

component of the LGS-controlled DM commands which lies in the span of the NGS-controlled modes. The details in the split tomography concept can be found in [16, 17].

3. LOW ORDER CONTROL

3.1 Low Order Modes

Multiple low order NGS WFS are required to control tip/tilt, focus, and plate scale modes. Plate scale modes arises from the fundamental inability of laser guide stars (LGS) to measure global tip and tilt. In the case of NFIRAOS, which employs two deformable mirrors (DMs) conjugated at 0 km and 11.8 km, there exist specific linear combinations of DM quadratic modes that project as field-dependent pure tip/tilt at the LGS wavefront sensors (WFS) and are therefore unobservable.

Let x_0, y_0 and x_{12}, y_{12} denote the x, y coordinates of actuators of DM0 and DM12. Let h_c be the conjugate range of DM12. The cone effect introduces a scaling factor $s_c = 1 - h_c/h_s$, where h_s is the source height (the sodium layer mean altitude for LGS WFS, and effectively inf for science evaluation direction ray tracing).

The six modes across the two DMs that are not reliably measured by the LGS WFS are given by:

$$M_1^0 = [x_0]; \quad M_1^{12} = [\mathbf{0}]; \quad (1)$$

$$M_2^0 = [y_0]; \quad M_2^{12} = [\mathbf{0}]; \quad (2)$$

$$M_3^0 = [x_0^2 + y_0^2]; \quad M_3^{12} = -[x_{12}^2 + y_{12}^2] / s_c^2; \quad (3)$$

$$M_4^0 = [x_0^2 - y_0^2]; \quad M_4^{12} = -[x_{12}^2 - y_{12}^2] / s_c^2; \quad (4)$$

$$M_5^0 = [x_0 \cdot y_0]; \quad M_5^{12} = -[x_{12} \cdot y_{12}] / s_c^2; \quad (5)$$

$$M_6^0 = [x_0^2 + y_0^2]; \quad M_6^{12} = [\mathbf{0}]; \quad (6)$$

where $[\mathbf{0}]$ denotes a zero vector of the same length as x_{12} . The scaling factor s_c accounts for the cone effect. The terms x^2, y^2 and $x \cdot y$ here denote element-wise operations. No tip/tilt or focus modes are applied to DM12, as they cannot be distinguished from the same modes applied to DM0.

It is obvious that M_1, M_2 , and M_6 produce pure tip/tilt (TT) or focus in LGS measurements, but it may not be immediately clear for the other three terms. To verify this, the optical path difference (OPD) for mode i at the pupil can be written as

$$OPD_i(x, y) = M_i^0(x, y) + M_i^{12}(x^{12}, y^{12}) \quad (7)$$

where (x, y) denotes the coordinates of the ray in the pupil and at its intersection with DM0. The coordinates (x^{12}, y^{12}) denote the location where the same ray intersects DM12.

3.2 LGS Observed

From simple geometric calculations, we can see that

$$(x^{12}, y^{12}) = (x, y) s_c + (\theta_x, \theta_y) h_c \quad (8)$$

Where (θ_x, θ_y) denotes the chief ray angle on sky. The OPDs for LGS are then given by

$$OPD_1^L(x, y) = x \quad (9)$$

$$OPD_2^L(x, y) = y \quad (10)$$

$$OPD_3^L(x, y) = -\left(2\theta_x \frac{h_c}{s_c} x + 2\theta_y \frac{h_c}{s_c} y\right) - (\theta_x^2 + \theta_y^2) \left(\frac{h_c}{s_c}\right)^2 \quad (11)$$

$$OPD_4^L(x, y) = -\left(2\theta_x \frac{h_c}{s_c} x - 2\theta_y \frac{h_c}{s_c} y\right) - (\theta_x^2 - \theta_y^2) \left(\frac{h_c}{s_c}\right)^2 \quad (12)$$

$$OPD_5^L(x, y) = -\left(\theta_y \frac{h_c}{s_c} x + \theta_x \frac{h_c}{s_c} y\right) - (\theta_x \theta_y) \left(\frac{h_c}{s_c}\right)^2 \quad (13)$$

$$OPD_6^L(x, y) = x^2 + y^2 \quad (14)$$

The resulting OPD in the LGS WFS for all three plate scale modes reduces to field dependent pure tip/tilt and therefore cannot be sensed.

3.3 Science directions

For science (or NGS) directions, propagating from infinity, we have

$$(x^{12}, y^{12}) = (x, y) + (\theta_x, \theta_y) h_c \quad (15)$$

Table 3. Availability of bright NGS for TT or TTF WFS and combination of modes controlled by the fast and slow loops

Bright NGS and fast loop WFS	Fast loop modes	Slow loop WFS	Slow loop modes
1 TTF	Tip/tilt/focus	1-2 TT	Plate scale only
1 TT	Tip/tilt	1 TTF, 0-1 TT	Focus and plate scale
1 TTF, 1-2 TT	all modes	-	-

The OPDs are then given by

$$OPD_1^S(x, y) = x \quad (16)$$

$$OPD_2^S(x, y) = y \quad (17)$$

$$OPD_3^S(x, y) = (x^2 + y^2) \left(1 - \frac{1}{s_c^2}\right) - 2(\theta_x x + \theta_y y) \frac{h_c}{s_c^2} - (\theta_x^2 + \theta_y^2) \left(\frac{h_c}{s_c}\right)^2 \quad (18)$$

$$OPD_4^S(x, y) = (x^2 - y^2) \left(1 - \frac{1}{s_c^2}\right) - 2(\theta_x x - \theta_y y) \frac{h_c}{s_c^2} - (\theta_x^2 - \theta_y^2) \left(\frac{h_c}{s_c}\right)^2 \quad (19)$$

$$OPD_5^S(x, y) = x.y \left(1 - \frac{1}{s_c^2}\right) - (\theta_y x + \theta_x y) \frac{h_c}{s_c^2} - (\theta_x \theta_y) \left(\frac{h_c}{s_c}\right)^2 \quad (20)$$

$$OPD_6^S(x, y) = x^2 + y^2 \quad (21)$$

The resulting OPD in the NGS WFS for all three plate scale modes reduces to field-dependent tip/tilt as well as second-order components, and therefore can be sensed either by multiple tip/tilt WFSs and/or a single 2x2 WFS (aka TTF WFS). However, the third and sixth modes cannot be separated if only a single 2x2 WFS is used.

3.4 Multi-rate Control

Figure 1 shows the cumulative probability of finding guide stars brighter than a given J-band magnitude within the NFIRAOS patrol field of view (1' radius). It is evident that the probability of finding three bright NGS is significantly lower than that of finding one or two bright NGS.

Figure 2 shows the power spectral density (PSD) of tip-tilt, total plate scale, and focus modes, along with the residual error for a given ideal rejection bandwidth. The tip-tilt modes include contributions from atmospheric turbulence, telescope wind shake, and mechanical vibrations, and therefore require the highest rejection bandwidth to achieve the desired residual error. In contrast, plate scale errors arise from matched combinations of second-order Zernike modes across different layers, and thus have the lowest bandwidth requirement.

Table 3 summarizes the availability of bright NGS for TT or TTF WFS, as well as the allocation of modes between the fast and slow loops depending on guide star availability. The sampling rates of the fast and slow loops are determined based on the estimated signal-to-noise ratio, which depends on the guide star brightness and its location within the patrol field of view.

To simplify the blending scheme, the coupling between the fast and slow loops is removed, such that the control output of one loop is not sensed by the other loop. The modes controlled by the slow loops, M_{slow} , are given by

$$M_{\text{slow}} = (I - G_{\text{Fast}}^\dagger G_{\text{Fast}})M \quad (22)$$

where G_{Fast} is the sensitivity matrix of the fast WFS for the modes controlled by the fast loop.

Figure 3 shows a comparison of sky coverage between single- and multi- rate control. Multi-rate control provides noticeable improvements and enhanced stability, as each WFS operates within a healthy signal-to-noise regime (e.g., $\text{SNR} > 5$). In contrast, under single-rate control, this condition may not be satisfied, and the WFS with dimmer guide stars can lose lock due to insufficient signal-to-noise ratio.

Figure 1. Cumulative probability of finding guide stars brighter than a given J-band magnitude within the NFIRAOS patrol field of view of 1' radius.

Figure 2. Power spectrum density of tip and tilt, total plate scale, and focus modes.

Figure 3. Comparison of sky coverage between single- and multi- rate control.

4. LOW ORDER CONTROL PERFORMANCE PREDICTION

To support observation planning for low-order NGS selection, the performance of each candidate asterism must be estimated on short timescales. Physical-optics sky coverage tools are computationally expensive, as they rely on time-domain simulations to evaluate each asterism. This makes them impractical for routine use by astronomers due to their substantial time and resource requirements.

To address this limitation, we adopt a machine learning-based approach to predict performance, trained on data generated from sky coverage simulations spanning a range of turbulence profile percentile and zenith angles. For each asterism, the following features are extracted for every guide star, together with the turbulence profile percentile, zenith angle, and resulting residual wavefront error:

- radial distance from the on-axis field point
- azimuthal angle relative to the first guide star (sorted in ascending order)
- J, H, and Ks magnitudes

The predicted performance of each candidate asterism can be obtained instantaneously via inference using the same set of input features readily available from the guide star catalog and the anticipated observing condition.

This is a typical scalar regression problem on multidimensional data, which is well suited to decision-tree based algorithms. We evaluated both Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM[20]) v4.6 and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost[21]) v3, and obtained comparable performance. The results presented here are based on LightGBM, as it provides marginally better performance. 80% of the input asterisms are used for training while the remaining 20% are reserved testing the inference performance.

Figure 4 shows the feature importance (left panel) and predicted vs. simulated results for both training and test data (right panel). Overall, the predictions show a strong correlation with the simulation results, with an RMS error of approximately 6%, which is acceptable for guide star selection since the ranking of asterisms is more important than the absolute performance prediction.

Figure 5 shows the comparison between predicted results (lines) and simulated results (crosses) for equilateral asterisms with equal magnitudes, shown for different star magnitudes, asterism radii, C_n^2 profile percentiles, and airmass. The overall trends appear reasonable, except for some artifacts that arise when the guide stars are near

Figure 4. Feature importance plot shows the relative weights assigned to different parameters. Predicted vs. simulated results shows good agreement for both training and test data.

the edge of the patrol field of view (radius 60”), where performance is poor and the training data coverage is limited.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we demonstrated the necessity and performance improvements of using a multi-rate controller for low-order NGS loops, since three sufficiently bright NGS are often unavailable. We also presented a machine learning-based approach that can predict the low-order correction performance of a given asterism instantaneously. The machine learning model is trained on physical optics sky coverage simulation results and achieves predictions with an RMS error of 6%.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The TIO Project gratefully acknowledges the support of the TIO Members and the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation. The Members and their respective collaborating institutions are as follows: California Institute of Technology (Caltech); the National Research Council of Canada (NRC); the Association of Canadian Universities for Research in Astronomy (ACURA); the Department of Science and Technology, Government of India (DST); the Department of Atomic Energy of India (DAE); the National Institute of Natural Sciences of Japan (NINS); the National Astronomical Observatory of Japan (NAOJ); and the Regents of the University of California (UC). This work was supported as well by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy (AURA) and U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF).

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Figure 5. Predicted results for equilateral asterisms with equal magnitudes, shown for different star magnitudes, C_n^2 profile percentiles, and airmass.

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